

A Study on Consumer Perception towards Online Shopping with Special Reference to Karimangalam Taluk

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the current scenario consumer perception towards online shopping of the key to the success of, opportunities and challenges in. Although environmental issues influence all human activities, few academic disciplines have integrated issues into their benefits. The research concludes to study and identify the consumer perception towards online shopping. The required data of study will be collected from both primary as well as secondary sources. The researcher has been used the well-structured questionnaire for the data collection. The researcher distributed about 150 questionnaires to sample design is convenient sampling methods. The findings and conclusions from this study are consumer perception of online shopping. There is growing interest among the customers all over the world regarding protection of the environment. Worldwide evidence indicates that people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior. Society's "new" concerns. Some businesses have been quick to accept concepts like environmental management systems waste minimization, and have integrated environmental issues into all organizational activities. One business area where environmental issues have received a great deal of discussion in the popular and professional press is marketing. Terms like "Green Marketing" and "Environmental Marketing" frequently appear in the popular press. Many governments around the world have become so concerned about green marketing activities that they have attempted to regulate them. There is growing interest among the consumers all over the world regarding protection of the environment. Worldwide evidence indicates people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior. As a result of this, green marketing has emerged which speaks for the growing market for sustainable and socially responsible products and services.

Keywords: Consumers, Technology, Online, Marketing

Introduction

Nowadays consumers are playing an important role in online shopping. The capacity of purchasing without leaving their place is of great interest to many consumers. The sharp increase of internet usage as well as the systematic progress of information technology has transformed the way the goods are bought and sold, resulting in the exponential growth in the number of online shoppers.

The Internet is a new information technology device that has brought a drastic change in the life of people. It has become a

part of modern life across the world. It has offered so many benefits such abundant information, convenience, time-saving; cost benefits, international brands, etc.

The World Wide Web (WWW) has grown incredibly since its inception in 1990 and by 1991 it was opened for commercial use. The internet explosion has opened the doors to a new electronic world, which facilitated in taking the business to another level. In the past, consumers were using the Internet for research work for exploring new options and for doing various studies, for communicating or doing professional work. The Internet is also used for online banking, and even shopping. Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce whereby consumers directly buy goods and services from a seller over the internet without any intermediary services. With the help of the internet, consumer found that they no longer need to accept the fixed prices for the products and services because, with just a click button, they can get goods and services at the lowest price with higher quality. It is important for online businesses interested in venturing into the online market to understand their consumers' perception towards online and what factors influence their shopping decisions.

The Internet is changing the way consumers shop and buy goods and services and has rapidly evolved into a global phenomenon. Many companies have started using the Internet the aim of cutting marketing costs, thereby reducing the price of their products and services to stay ahead in highly competitive markets. Without the doubt, the Internet has influenced our lives deeply in which it plays an indispensable and irreplaceable role. Many experts are optimistic about the prospect of online business. In addition to the tremendous potential of the E-commerce market, the Internet provides a unique opportunity for companies to more efficiently reach existing and potential customers.

The Internet has made it so flexible and convenient for companies to approach consumers and vice versa around the clock 24*7. If the Internet is anything to go by, India's technological and economic growth has moved into the top gear. With more India's online shopping registering a phenomenal 100 percent annual growth, many retail chains and durable consumer companies are joining the Web bandwagon to tap the e-shopping market."The online shopping industry in India is fast catching on, not just in the larger metros but also in, the smaller cities. At present the market is estimated at Rs.46,000crore and is growing at 100 percent per year," Ajit Chauhan, managing director, Synergy Promotions and Marketing Services, said.

Importance of the Study

Online shopping saves the people from overwork of hopping from one shop to another to buy the items they require. However, with so many online retailers selling a large verity of products, it becomes impossible for even online shoppers to decide what to buy and from where.

Due to the availability of convenience in online shopping, the consumer's are getting attracted to the modern method of shopping

Moreover, from the consumer point of view trust, worthiness and safety are considered to be the important phenomenon. To understand consumer's perception of online shopping and factors which influence it, a deep study is made at karimanagalam.

Statement of the Problem

One of the great concerned is trust and security. While one of the significant factors in electronic commerce is trust. To increase online shopping in karimangalam. Understanding consumer online shopping behavior and factors influencing this behavior when shopping online should be given priority. Researches indicate that majority ofkarimangalam (76%) especially young people were using the internet for non-shopping activities such as seeking information, entertainment, playing

games and communication with others. There are some barriers which have contributed to the unwillingness of karimangalam people because they are afraid that their personal information will be stolen by others. Despite the potential in karimangalam people, there is still a lack of understanding of online shopping in karimangalam. Hence, the researcher felt that there is a need to make an attempt to study the online shopping practices prevailing among people of karimangalam and their corresponding perception towards it.

Objectives

- To find out the preferences of the consumer regarding the attributes of the online shopping website.
- To find out the factors that influence the consumers to online shopping.
- To know the perception of the consumers towards online shopping.

The Scope of the Study

The study covers consumers who do online shopping frequently in karimangalam area and they are supposed to have experience in online shopping. The study was undertaken with a sample of 150 respondents.

Rajesh and Purushothaman (2013) in the holiday season, online shopping saves an individual the hassle of searching several stores and then waiting in long queues to buy a particular item. Many companies have started using the Internet with the aim of cutting marketing costs, thereby reducing the price of their products and services to stay ahead in highly competitive markets. That consumer buys goods from the online shopping website by factors like offers and discounts, the variety of product available, free home delivery, website user-friendliness.

Prerna Kumar, (2013) In the era of Internet technology, Wi-fi services and smart-phone gadgets, online promotion tools are very effective in reaching out to the target audience. They are perceived to be effective, informative and credible. Online promotions have the potential to engage the audience in impulsive behavior. Although, users sometimes find online promotions to cause irritability, yet they are convincing. The beauty of technology is in the usage of visuals and information. Companies must exploit this feature of the Internet through the usage of colored pictures and images of the entire product.

Namita Bhandari (2013) With Internet penetration improving in the country, smart phones becoming affordable and lifestyles becoming hectic, the way people used to shop is changing. Also with a huge chunk of the young and working population, Indian demographics are a delight for e-commerce retailers. But to gain the trust and attention of Indian consumers in this virtual shopping world, there are many aspects of consumer behavior which need to be explored. What exactly is Indian consumer thinking when he is buying online, what are his expectations, apprehensions, anxieties and phobias which e-retailers need to overcome?

Seinajoenammattikorkeakoulu (2013) Online consumers are always seeking new products, new attractiveness and the most important thing being price compatibility with their budget. The Internet is the best way to save time and money by purchasing online within their range of budget at home or anywhere. Online consumers don't have limits to online shopping. They also use the Internet for comparison of prices of goods and services, news, visit social networks and search for information and so on. Online shopping behavior depends on variables, Internet knowledge, and experience and last factor are shopping incentives.

Minjoon Jun (2013) Online consumers to identify the attributes of online shopping convenience and then develop and validate and five dimensions of online shopping convenience are access, search, evaluation, transaction, and possession/post-purchase convenience. This instrument can

assist managers in identifying and overcoming key obstacles to the delivery of a highly convenient online shopping service to consumers, and also helps them enlarge their loyal consumer base.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is a way to systematically source the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is scientifically done. The process used to collect information and data to make business decisions. The methodology may include publication research, interview, surveys and other research techniques and could include both present and historical information.

Research methodology is a collective term for the structured process of conducting research. There are many different methodologies used in various types of research and the term is used to include research design, data gathering and data analysis.

Research Design

The research design is used for this study is descriptive design. Descriptive research design includes surveys and fact-finding enquires of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is the description of the state of affairs, as it exists at present.

Sources of Data Collection

Primary Data

The primary data has collected the help of well-constructed questionnaire method and also used an interview schedule.

Secondary Data

Secondary data, on the other hand, for those who have already been passed through the statistical process. The secondary data was collected from books, journals and websites.

Sampling

Sampling is a process of selecting a sufficient number of elements from the large groups. It is used to limit the number of representatives where as the census is used for covering large population.

Sample Design

“A sample design is the theoretical basis and practical means by which we infer the characteristics of some population by generalizing from the sample of relatively few of the units comprising the population.”

When population elements are selected for inclusion in the sample based on the ease of access it can be called as convenience sampling.

Sample Size

Among the total population of consumers, a sample of 150 respondents was selected to direct relevant information for the study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 4.1 Age of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Below 20	34	22.7
21-30	72	48.0
31-40	41	27.3
Above 41	3	2.0
Total	150	100.0

Age is a significant factor in the life of the human being as it reflects the maturity level of an individual and is an important variable in any research. It is evident from the table 4.1 that most of the respondents, i.e., 48 percentage belong to the age group of 21 to 30, and 27 percentage of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40, 22.7 percentage of the respondents belong to the age group of below 20, and 2 percentage of the respondents belong to the age group of above 41. Therefore, the respondents who are in between the age group of 21 to 30 are the highest in number.

Table 4.2 Gender of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Male	77	51.3
Female	73	48.7
Total	150	100.0

The study on the gender of respondents is very important in any research as it determines the factors influence online shopping. It is seen from table 4.2 presents that 51.3 percentage of the respondents are male and the other 48.7 percentage of the respondents are female. Hence, male respondents are more than the female.

Table 4.7 The preferable Online Site for Online Shopping

	Frequency	Percent
Flipkart	63	42.0
Snapdeal	28	18.7
Jabong	14	9.3
Amazon	28	18.7
Homeshop18	15	10.0
Others	2	1.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 4.7 clearly shows the preference of online shopping site by the respondents, 42 percentage of the respondents prefer Flipkart as their most favorite website, 18.7 percentage of the respondents prefer both Amazon and Snapdeal website, ten percentage of the respondents prefer Homeshop18. Therefore, it is evident that from the above table the most of the respondents prefer Flipkart than any other shopping websites.

Table 4.8 Influencing Factor

	Frequency	Percent
Advertisement	32	21.3
Friends	81	54.0
Family and Relatives	36	24.0
Others	1	.7
Total	150	100.0

Table 4.8 shows as to how the respondents come to know online shopping. Out of 150 respondents, the highest no. of respondents get induced to do online shopping through friends and their percentage is 54. Next, to them, 36 respondents induced by their family and relatives. This is the second highest percentage in number. The least no. of respondents gets induced through advertisements.

Table 4.9 The Frequency of Online Purchasing

	Frequency	Percent
One time	51	34.0
Two times	48	32.0
Three times	28	18.7
More than three times	23	15.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 4.9 the frequency of online purchasing by the sample respondents shows among 150 respondents, 34 percentage of the respondents purchased through online shopping only once, 32 percentage of the respondents purchased twice, 18.7 percentage of the respondents purchased thrice, and 15.3 percentage of the respondents purchased more than three times.

Chi-Square Tests

Ho: There is no relationship between gender and influencing factor

H1: There is a relationship between gender and influencing factor

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.242a	3	.524
Likelihood Ratio	2.634	3	.452
Linear-by-Linear Association	.526	1	.468
N of Valid Cases	150		

2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .49.

By comparing the calculated value with the table value, the conclusion is made as follows;

The above table shows the level of significance value is (0.559) which is more than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is (Ho) is accepted. There is no relationship between the gender of the respondents and the influencing factor are independent.

Findings

1. Nearly two fourth (48%) of the respondents belong to the age group of 21-30.
2. More than two fourth (51.3%) of the respondents are male.
3. More than two fourth (58.7%) of the respondents are unmarried.
4. More than two fourth (51%) of the respondents purchased through online shopping only once.
5. more than two fourth (55%) of the respondents purchase books through online shopping.
6. More than one third (38.7%) of the respondents prefer online shopping due to home delivery.
7. More than one third (38.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed online shopping leads to quick shopping.
8. Nearly two fourth (47.3%) of the respondents agreed that online shopping provides convenience.
9. Nearly two fourth (46%) of the respondents agreed that online shopping offers products for the better price.
10. Nearly two fourth (47.3%) of the respondents agreed that online shopping offers customer service.

Suggestion

Online shopping should be made as consumer friendly. Online shopping should be made affordable to the middle-class people. After sale service and warranty, the system should be made as consumer friendly. The consumer should be given an opportunity to see and Variety the products which are purchased through online. The researcher also learned that the products are not delivered in certain places. So, online shopping should facilitate a wide delivery of products, so that the number of people could purchase products through online shopping.

Conclusion

The research study reveals that specifically the younger generations who are in the age groups of 21 to 30 are mostly and frequently engaged in the process of online shopping. No doubt, the factors viz., quality, discount, simple payment methods, less expensive are the factors influenced the online buyers and account for consumer satisfaction. The present study gave insight into what the consumers perceived as important attributes of online shopping, factors that influenced consumers to shop online, their level of satisfaction towards the products offered in online and their perception towards the online sites/Apps.

It is found that personal characteristics significantly affect online shopping attitudes, intention, and behavior. The result of the present study shows that the perception of online shoppers influences their intention to buy through online. The present study clearly shows that the interest among the young generation is more towards online shopping and this will be increasing shortly. This will certainly pose a great challenge to the traditional shopping mode. Therefore, there will be a counter challenge from the traditional shopping side, and this will again accelerate the growth of online shopping.

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